

ABITARE IL BOSCO

A MANIFESTO FOR THE INTEGRATION OF FORESTS INTO COMMUNITIES

Preface

The FAO Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020¹ estimates that forests cover a total area of 4.1 billion hectares worldwide, equal to 31% of the Earth's land surface (almost half a hectare per person, if distribution were homogeneous). Forests also cover almost one third of the national territory in Italy (36.7%); however, while at the global level forested areas tend to decrease (178 million hectares of forests and woodlands have been lost since 1990), in Italy their extent has increased.

From the perspective of landscape and land use, **forests and woodlands constitute significant portions of territory. Moreover, through them, communities benefit from ecosystem services that are fundamental for life and the well-being of the planet**, including (see the Manifesto for Systemic Silviculture²): conservation of soil and water resources, biodiversity protection, climate change mitigation, the fight against desertification, the possibility of obtaining timber and non-timber products, as well as biomass for energy production.

Wooded areas are the object of a variety of representations that oscillate between benevolent views, in which the forest is seen as a welcoming and providential place (often used as a setting for fairy tales and stories and from which communities derive resources and benefits of various kinds), and views in which the forest takes on the connotations of a dark, wild environment hostile to humans. However, these different representations do not reflect the current conditions of forested areas. In Italy, as in the rest of Europe, the terms "woodland" and "forest" both identify portions of land surface characterised by the presence of high forest vegetation (trees and shrubs). In the past, the term woodland referred to forested areas closer to settlements, reachable on foot and cultivated, while the term forest (which not by chance retains in its etymology the reference to what "lies outside") referred to more remote and wild wooded areas. Today, this distinction has completely faded: regardless of their location, there is no environmental reality characterised by the presence of high forest vegetation that has not been manipulated by humans at some point in the past. In Italy, this *status quo* has also been formally recognised by legislation. Legislative Decree 34/2018 (the Consolidated Forestry Act) **established that the terms woodland, forest and selva may be used as synonyms.**

In Italy, woodlands and forests are present throughout the country, particularly in Tuscany (10.4% of the national forest area), Piedmont (9.8%) and Lombardy (8.7%).

At the national level, the Re Soil Foundation—promoted by the University of Bologna, Coldiretti, Novamont and the Polytechnic of Turin—calculated that between 2005 and 2015 forest area increased by 587,000 hectares, reaching a total of 11 million hectares, while biomass increased by 18.4% (from 144.9 m³ per

¹ See: <https://www.fao.org/3/CA8753EN/CA8753EN.pdf>

² See: <https://aisfdotit.files.wordpress.com/2013/06/manifesto.pdf>

hectare to 165.4)³. As a result, the stock of stored organic carbon increased from 490 million to 569 million tonnes, and CO₂ removed from the atmosphere rose from 1,798 million to 2,088 million tonnes (+290 million tonnes)⁴.

This is an apparently positive picture, which nevertheless does not fully describe the condition of forests and woodlands. In Italy today, forested areas are largely abandoned and not governed from the perspective of territorial planning. In 2021 alone, almost 159,000 hectares of forest burned. This represents a social loss, in addition to environmental and economic damage, in which climate change is a relevant contributing factor, but not necessarily the most important one. Long periods of heat and drought tend to favour the spread of wildfires, whose origin is, however, usually attributable to human action.

According to Coldiretti⁵, in order to safeguard and protect forests from the risks to which they are exposed (in addition to fires, other relevant risks include extreme weather events, land consumption and the spread of diseases, such as in the case of African swine fever), it is first of all necessary to counter the abandonment of rural areas by agricultural entrepreneurs and to enhance the functions of surveillance, maintenance and territorial management carried out by them. An opportunity may come from investments in support of local timber supply chains, with a consequent increase in domestic demand for wood. Italy currently imports more than 80% of the wood needed by the furniture and paper industries, as well as for heating. “The Italian timber industry is the first in Europe, but it relies on wood coming from neighbouring countries such as Austria, France, Switzerland and Germany, demonstrating a great untapped economic potential” (Coldiretti - National Confederation of Italian Farmers).

Forests can be managed through two different forms of governance: high forest and coppice. In both cases, various forms of management practices may be applied. In high forest systems, temporal continuity is ensured through sexual reproduction, with seeds giving rise to new plants. When managed under even-aged systems, high forests are characterised by long rotation periods. In coppice systems, trees are perpetuated through vegetative reproduction, ensured by the resprouting of shoots that grow from stumps after cutting. In this case, rotation periods are short. Recently, however, there has been an increase in spontaneous forests, which are reoccupying spaces once used for traditional agro-silvo-pastoral activities that have been abandoned.

Greater stewardship of forests, even when aimed at their economic exploitation, makes it possible to achieve positive ecosystem outcomes. In addition to timber production, forests play a fundamental role in capturing CO₂ present in the atmosphere, thereby contributing to the balancing of ecosystem equilibrium. Forests abandoned to themselves, however, constitute a factor of degradation and risk for the territory and become less efficient from the point of view of CO₂ sequestration.

From the perspective of a sustainable rethinking of the country’s current development model, forests emerge as privileged areas of study and action. Through them, it is possible to imagine new forms of coexistence with nature, simultaneously pursuing objectives of economic growth and nature conservation. Beyond their historical-cultural value, aesthetic and landscape significance, and recreational function, forests are increasingly appreciated for their ecosystem properties and their role in climate regulation. At the centre of current interest lies in particular their capacity to capture atmospheric CO₂ and mitigate the ecological footprint of the nearby settlements.

³ Source: <https://resoilfoundation.org/bioeconomia-circolare/boschi-italiani-crescono-luci-ombre/>

⁴ Data from Inventario Nazionale delle Foreste e dei Serbatoi forestali di Carbonio (National Inventory of Forests and Forest Carbon Sinks). See: <https://www.sian.it/inventarioforestale>

⁵ <https://www.coldiretti.it/>

Hence **the aim of this Manifesto** to activate an **open, positive, operational and locally participated discussion** on forests, catalysing—in ways that are commensurate with the specific characteristics of places and of the current historical period—**interest and consensus around a limited number of paradigmatic orientations**.

The first of these orientations, or **new forest paradigms**, concerns the need for communities to imagine **new ways of living with the forest and entering into harmony with it**, by deepening their knowledge of it and **sharing its destinies**, rather than seeking to appropriate it to satisfy their own needs. From this perspective, the literature identifies an additional form of value attribution, according to which nature is considered on a par with a member of the community inhabiting a given territory.

The second orientation concerns the need to **actively involve local communities** in relation to their forests. Such involvement **also engages emotions, environmental education and awareness-raising**. In practical terms, it requires **identifying the most appropriate ways to ensure that people feel involved and co-responsible for the care of the forest**.

In this process, an important starting point is represented by the Manifesto for Systemic Silviculture promoted by the Italian Academy of Forest Sciences (AISF)⁶, which emphasises the importance of forest management planning and the widespread application of the principles of *systemic silviculture*, extended to forest operators as well as to local administrators and landowners. In this Manifesto, as in the one promoted by AISF, the objective is to foster the **active participation of communities**.

This Manifesto, in particular, is addressed to the territories that host parts of this fundamental heritage and to their administrators, in order to emphasise the urgency of a **sustainable sharing of forest values and of the problems related to their management**, through the **shared definition of objectives and operational intentions** to be implemented through pilot projects and a combined scientific and design-oriented network of ad hoc interventions.

A manifesto for...

I. Sharing the values of the forest

The subject of this Manifesto is the forest understood as a wooded portion of territory, with respect to which communities develop different forms of interaction and specific attributions of meaning and value. The representation that derives from this relationship depends primarily on the characteristics of the community and on the ways in which it relates to the forest, but also on how it conceives the natural environment. For example, in matters of forest management, it is not uncommon for decisions taken by those responsible for this function (public administrators or private owners) to oscillate between contrasting ideological positions, according to which human intervention is at times considered indispensable and at other times unnecessary, if not harmful.

Certainly, a **first way of looking at the forest** corresponds to an anthropocentric and utilitarian vision of nature. According to this vision, the forest acquires value and deserves to be cared for by communities by virtue of the material products it provides. Forest management practices themselves refer to the instrumental value of the forest. At the basis of the “classical” vision of forestry and forest management lies the intention to establish criteria and intervention practices capable of maximising and stabilising timber

⁶ Downloadable at sito <https://aisfdotit.files.wordpress.com/2013/06/manifesto.pdf>

production over time. Traditionally, the main focus of forest management has been the production of construction timber, while wood for energy purposes, such as pellets, has been considered only secondarily. In addition, forests produce various types of minor products (mushrooms, small fruits, shrubs, medicinal herbs etc.), whose harvesting is only partially regulated and which largely remain within local circuits of self-consumption.

Today, the vision that links the value of the forest exclusively to its productive efficiency tends to be replaced by a **more holistic vision**, which considers both material and immaterial products, such as the services and ecological functions that benefit human well-being and the entire ecosystem.

A second way of looking at the forest (rare within silvicultural approaches, but present in territorial and environmental conservation policies) recognises its intrinsic value, independently of the goods it produces. This vision falls within a biocentric approach to nature and is associated with a broader movement of rediscovering sustainability as a global strategy for growth and development. Over recent decades, new productive and social functions and roles attributed to forests by society have led to an increase in their importance, but also in the complexity of forest management. The institutional and regulatory framework—at Italian, European and global levels—has acknowledged forest multifunctionality, and forest management has increasingly shifted towards less rigid silvicultural approaches and adaptive planning methods (among the most recent policy directions produced in Italy, it is worth noting the adoption in February 2022 of the *National Forestry Strategy*, with a twenty-year timeframe⁷).

Unlike other types of territorial assets subject to human intervention and policy action (infrastructure, buildings, etc.), the forest is a living and dynamic component. The forest is a living biological system and, as such, prefigures a subject of rights that must be protected, conserved and defended. Moreover, it actively interacts with abiotic and biotic dimensions from multiple perspectives, contributing to **biodiversity, landscape and the production of ecosystem externalities (goods and services)**.

From the perspective of this Manifesto, the forest has value with respect to all these dimensions, all of which contribute to forming a sustainable vision of the forest and of its development over time.

In particular:

1. the forest is recognised as having a historical-cultural, aesthetic-landscape and recreational significance;
2. the forest is recognised as playing a key role in socio-economic development, environmental protection, and the production of goods and services;
3. attention is paid to forest-related needs, both current and those of future generations;
4. the forest is recognised as a living entity that has value in and of itself;
5. the forest is recognised as a shared heritage, whose conservation also assumes an ethical meaning;
6. forest management is framed within the general criterion of environmental protection, regulated at national and European levels, which implies prevention, precaution, ecological, economic and social sustainability.

However, the balancing of these different values cannot be decided *a priori* or in a universal manner: it depends on the specific territorial conditions in which the forest is embedded and on the particular relationships it establishes with the local communities of reference. The values of the forest must be co-

⁷ <https://www.reterurale.it/foreste/StrategiaForestaleNazionale>

constructed within the community, through a process of sharing that recognises the forest as a constitutive component of the territory and of its development.

Our way of living is individual, but also collective, and the forested natural environment is part of the community we inhabit and of which we are made. The other—the environment—is part of us: we are made of it, because our individual lives would be impossible without it. Life draws its existence from the context in which we are immersed, from the land we inhabit and which, in turn, inhabits us: if we abandon something, the land incorporates it; if we take something (such as air, water or food), it comes from the land. Through direct experience of the forest, this relationship becomes more clearly perceptible.

II. Outlining the framework of opportunities and challenges of forest areas

Although the international scientific and political community is moving towards a new conception of the forest, which appreciates and recognises its different values, practices of forest control and care have progressively declined worldwide. In Italy as well, due to the combined effect of economic pressures (lack of funding and limited profitability of forests), political factors (limited attention from government and institutions) and institutional issues (fragmentation and difficult attribution of ownership), forest management practices have significantly weakened.

On the one hand, the abandonment of traditional livestock breeding and farming practices in mountain and hill areas (for example, terraced cultivation) has led to the disappearance of informal practices of forest surveillance and maintenance once carried out by agricultural entrepreneurs and residents, leaving room for the advance of secondary forests over areas abandoned by agriculture. Drawing on FAO data, Meoni (2020) notes that in Italy—also thanks to the expansion of new spontaneously regenerating forests—there have never been so many forests for centuries. Especially in mountain areas, the progressive abandonment of agro-forestry activities in favour of more profitable activities (industry and crafts) has led to a reduction in silvicultural interventions, which in turn has **limited the bio-ecological efficiency of forests. Other factors have also contributed to degradation, including the increased frequency of fires, uncontrolled grazing practices, and irrational forest exploitation.**

On the other hand, public authorities have also reduced resources and, consequently, their capacity to steward the territory. The forest has shifted from being a place of care to becoming an uncultivated area, from a resource to a risk. The main problems associated with this process—partly accelerated by rapid climate change—are wildfires, infestations (parasites and alien plant species), and hydrogeological instability.

In the face of these problems, territories have the opportunity to reclaim a portion of land that contributes significantly to countering current threats and to locally building a new model of sustainable development. The classical approach to silviculture and forest management, however, has simplified forest systems in order to make production predictable and controllable and to achieve maximum land rent. This has resulted in a levelling and homogenisation of supply and in greater exposure to competition. Within the new emerging perspective, forests must also be valued in relation to their specific characteristics and potential, as well as to the expectations of resident populations. This renewed attention to the social and cultural functions of forests makes their management more meaningful, but also more complex. For this reason, alongside technical guidelines for sustainable forest planning and maintenance, it is necessary to envisage a broader model of action. Within this model, not only wide and diversified participation of territorial actors is required—actors who, through their participation, undertake a genuine educational and cultural pathway in relation to forests—but also the networking of initiatives launched across different forest systems.

The guiding principles of this new practice:

7. the forest is a complex biological system that requires complex management tools as well as short-, medium- and long-term perspectives;
8. the forest is a territorial system that requires planning interventions at different territorial levels;
9. the forest performs functions of public interest and must therefore be protected by communities for communities;
10. the forest is a shared heritage to be transmitted to future generations in optimal conditions;
11. the forest is a universal heritage that must be protected for the functional efficiency of the ecosystem and the sustainability of the entire planet;
12. without human interventions of care and management, forests already in the short term are subject to processes of biodiversity loss and degradation;
13. the practice of forest management planning organises over time and space the management and use of forest stands in order to guarantee, in the present and in the future, their main ecological, economic and social functions.

III. Recognising a system of objectives and priorities that brings forests back to the centre of communities and politics

In addressing the challenge of a new model for the management of forest areas—as an example of a broader way of understanding the relationship between human communities and nature, and between society and the natural environment—it is necessary to pay attention to the history, specific characteristics, narratives and value systems that characterise individual forests. As initial operational indications, in order to ensure that the current model of forest intervention aligns with the directions and principles outlined in the previous sections of the Manifesto, it is considered appropriate to:

14. bring people back to experiencing forests, according to approaches that originate from territories and communities, also working on aspects such as empathy and the sharing of a common project, therefore through co-design;
15. acknowledge that there is no codified forest, no predefined model towards which forest stands should tend, regardless of their natural dynamism: each intervention must be assessed on a case-by-case basis;
16. intervene in forests to contribute to local development, as well as to the safeguarding of biodiversity, landscape and externalities;
17. adopt the principles of systemic forestry, which aims at the functional efficiency of the ecosystem;
18. adopt an ecosystem approach to promote the equitable conservation and sustainable use of forest natural resources;
19. select silvicultural interventions on the basis of biological, ecological and territorial assessments;
20. protect forests from threats such as wildfires and other adverse events, including extreme climatic events (such as Storm Vaia), floods, infestations caused by pathogenic agents (viruses, bacteria, insects), etc., which may compromise forest stability and survival;

21. ensure widespread, sustainable and safe forms of access to forests for citizens and visitors, as well as for operators;
22. protect forests from neglect, which increases risk;
23. choose, in line with the principles of systemic forestry, cautious, continuous and widespread approaches to action, opposed to pre-established schemes but shaped to local specificities, and accompanied by monitoring of induced transformations.

The new model of intervention proposed by the Manifesto moves towards the enhancement of the territory in all its components: from natural and ecosystem components to social ones, belonging to the communities that inhabit it, according to a **systemic and responsible approach to the relationship between human communities and nature, and between environment and society**. It is a vision based on participation, sharing, and the construction of active and responsible citizenship. A vision that brings resources into a coherent system and generates outcomes that benefit everyone, including future generations. From this perspective, the **natural resource** represented by forest areas becomes the element around which reflections on well-being, health, balance and sustainability can be developed. Numerous benefits (sport-related, recreational, relaxing and meditative) derive for people from contact with and frequent use of forests, by virtue of their historical, naturalistic and landscape dimensions. On the basis of these properties, the Manifesto seeks to promote and encourage positive and responsible behaviours, fostering forms of tourism and lifestyles that are sustainable both for people and for the environment. Moving to the concrete level of silvicultural and forest management practices that can be immediately placed at the centre of discussion within communities, the following are highlighted:

24. the choice to opt for exclusively natural forest regeneration;
25. the choice to enhance forest persistence and to recover traditional forms of forest use, developed over time through local knowledge and oriented towards sustainability;
26. the choice to promote forest associations in order to address the problems of small-scale and fragmented forest ownership;
27. the choice to introduce forms of certification for forest product.

IV. Networking to transform intentions into projects and to experiment, across territories, a renewed relationship between human communities and nature

Forests must be cared for and inhabited through a community-based project, as a collective good that contributes to local development, providing co-benefits of different kinds:

- environmental: contribution of forest areas to CO₂ mitigation; calculation of the ecological footprint balance (biocapacity–ecological footprint of residents); preparation of environmental reports (available material and immaterial resources and existing impacts, etc.);
- socio-economic: census of currently existing economic activities, human resources and their trends; analysis of territorial resources (structural assets, commons, cultural resources, savoir-faire, etc.);
- infrastructural: assessment of the state of material and immaterial infrastructure networks (including ultra broadband-UBB); analysis of strengths, gaps and weaknesses;

- institutional and participatory: identification of institutional references for launching the project; tools and interlocutors at different scales; actors with whom to build and develop the project; construction of a training pathway; long-term governance.

Forests, even when limited in size, remain highly complex and dynamic realities, difficult to fully understand without the possibility of experiencing them continuously and appreciating both seasonal changes and longer-term transformations. For this reason as well, this Manifesto supports, as a *modus operandi*, the active involvement of local populations in project activities themselves, through the collection of testimonies (via interviews, questionnaires, life stories and focus groups) and the creation of an extended working group involving the many actors and subjects who inhabit, experience, know and, in various ways, act within the territory

In Italy, several experiences of forest management and planning are currently active which—already oriented towards an interpretation of the forest as a component of the local community—can be adopted to experiment with the paradigms and approaches conveyed by this Manifesto. For example, with reference to Piedmont, potential pilot cases can be identified in the Protected Area of Bosco delle Sorti – La Communa (AT), in the Bosco delle Sorti della Partecipanza of Trino Vercellese, in the Protected Natural Area of the Boschi delle Rocche del Roero, and others.

Similar contexts represent potential and promising settings in which to test, through pilot projects, new and innovative modes of forest management by communities. By operating in this way, the forest is placed at the centre of a participatory process of knowledge, sharing and sustainable development, replicable in other contexts.

The analysis of planning documents emerges, in particular, as the first fundamental step for setting up a community-based project, drafting project guidelines for the simultaneous safeguarding and enhancement of forests, and promoting sustainable pathways of local development.

The idea supported by the Manifesto is that of launching a series of pilot projects that can be scaled up and that contribute to creating coordination at a supra-local level (initially regional and subsequently national) among cared-for forests. A national network of cared-for forests would constitute the laboratory within which to refine the exchange of good practices; the enhancement method could itself become a driver of economic development, positioning itself within the international circuit of sustainable tourism. In the view of the Manifesto's signatories, the future of the environmental and ecological transition cannot be achieved through technological and infrastructural investments alone. Innovative solutions such as nature-based solutions (NBS) and "biocities" (Meoni, 2020) may certainly produce specific results, but if the objective is a different conception of the very relationship that human communities establish with the surrounding natural ecosystem (of which forests and woodlands constitute a predominant component), it is necessary to modify the way in which nature is locally valued and experienced.

In practical terms, this means realising, in the concrete implementation of a selection of contexts chosen for the launch of pilot projects, a double movement that—moving from the general to the particular and vice versa—applies to the selected communities and forests the principles and objectives of the Manifesto and then transforms, with the support of intermediary and territorial bodies such as foundations, the evidence collected into observations and general indications for action.

Below are some observations regarding the steps necessary for defining and implementing pilot projects:

28. identifying the case(s) study on which to initiate the pilot research–action aimed at the sustainable reappropriation of forests by the community;

29. identifying the objectives to be pursued, both general and specific, clearly **defining project intentions at multiple levels** and specifying the areas of intervention. The general objective is the enhancement of forest resources and of the territory's natural, ecosystem, landscape and cultural resources; it is appropriate to conduct an analysis and interpretation of the area that highlights **critical issues and opportunities**, indicating which project pathways to pursue;
30. carrying out, with the support of actors from the involved communities, an in-depth analysis of resources, characteristics, management modes, activities and assets of interest within the area, as well as its problems, difficulties and fragilities. From the **integrated reading of these values and constraints**, it becomes possible to identify which resources can stand out as **levers for development, change and project action**, and which **weak and problematic aspects** can consequently be addressed and resolved;
31. once the elements to be enhanced, the potential resources to be activated and the critical issues to be addressed have been identified, proceeding to: drafting the project plan, defining the methodology, identifying stakeholders, creating an extended working group, and defining timelines, milestones, intermediate and final objectives.

The Manifesto is publicly presented and open for signature by anyone—citizens, administrators or economic operators—who shares it and intends to actively contribute, within their own activities and in network with other signatories, to its implementation.

From the Manifesto and from the work carried out for its dissemination and signature, the possibility is expected to emerge of achieving objectives at multiple levels of action:

macro-level: the Manifesto promotes a renewed forest culture based on the concepts of community, responsible management, sustainability, and care/enhancement of the territory. In this sense, it proposes itself as a reference document for the production of scientific and popular publications on the condition of Italian forests and woodlands, including school textbooks at all levels;

meso-level: the Manifesto opens the way to the design and implementation of pilot initiatives which—particularly addressed to forest management experiences in Italy that already rely on formalised planning tools (e.g. Forest Management Plans) and previous experiences of community-based management—may represent the first step towards the affirmation of a new practice in forest planning and governance;

micro-level: the Manifesto identifies in the involvement of the local community—which reconnects with its historical foundations and becomes custodian of the heritage and the resources of its forests—the driving force of a new virtuous way of thinking about the relationship between human communities and nature.

Turin, February 3, 2026 (original version July 26, 2022)

Signatories and promoters (list updated to February 2026)

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To join the Manifesto as an individual, it is sufficient to complete the [form online](#) available at the following address <https://forms.gle/MBaEqtCDCsJcVpHK7> or send a request by email to abitareilbosco@gmail.com, explicitly stating that the applicant has read the information notice on the processing of personal data (see the Manifesto’s privacy policy published on the Association’s website).

An example of text for individual joining is as follows:

I, the undersigned Name xx Surname xxx, request to join the Manifesto “Abitare il Bosco”, authorising the publication of my name and surname among the Manifesto’s signatories. I hereby also confirm that I have read the [privacy information](#) published on the website of the InCreaSe Association.

For signatures by institutions and associations, please complete and send by email to abitareilbosco@gmail.com the specific [form published on the InCreaSe website](#)

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